

SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE IN THE KOKAND KHANATE IN THE LATE XIX AND EARLY XX CENTURIES.

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ABSTRACT

This article briefly describes the social life of the Kokand Khanate, which ruled in our country, ie the structure of the land, taxes and obligations, as well as the cultural life of the khanate: the work of writers.

The social system of the Kokand khanate also did not differ from the neighboring states. The palace officials and religious leaders, who were considered the upper class, owned large estates and land and water. The most numerous and least privileged strata of society were the common people. All the material wealth of the country was created by their labor. The highest military official in the khanate was the Emir of the army, and in most cases people of Kipchak descent were appointed to this position. The base of the army was also formed by the Kipchaks. The army was divided into tens of thousands, thousands, hundreds according to the rules of the time. For military-administrative officials, the palace treasury provided an annual salary and property in the form of "tanho" and "tarkhan".[1]

The share of agriculture in the economy was very high. Adequate water resources in

the territory of the khanate would be the basis for high yields from agriculture. Grain growing, melon growing, horticulture, vegetable growing, rice growing are well developed here. By the 19th century, the cotton fields in the khanate began to expand. The main buyer of cotton was Russia. The main lands of the khanate were state property. The largest landowner in the state was the khan, who owned large tracts of land, pastures, handicraft workshops, and shops. Livestock is also an important sector of the country's economic life, especially in the mountainous areas inhabited by nomadic Kyrgyz. [2] The khanate had all kinds of handicrafts typical of the Central Asian region: textiles, pottery, blacksmithing, coppersmithing, carpentry, and others. This sector of the economy is especially well developed in the large cities of Kokand, Tashkent, Andijan, Margilan, Osh, Khojand, Turkestan. In particular,

Kokand was famous for its blacksmiths, coppersmiths, Chust doppidoz, Rishtan pottery, Shahrikhan knives, Margilan silk and silk fabrics. Despite the difficult political situation in the khanate, which hindered the development of trade, trade played an important role in the economy of the country. Kokand, Margilan, Andijan, Tashkent, Shymkent, Uratapa and other cities were known as major shopping centers. Economic and trade relations between cities and villages were an important factor determining the development of domestic trade in the country. Domestic products played a key role in domestic trade relations. Imported products include various metals, factory products (from Russia), tea (from China and India), and some handicrafts imported from neighboring countries. [3] The basis of products exported to foreign markets are agricultural products (cotton, wool, yarn, fabrics, dried fruits, etc.), which began to be exported directly to Russia in the XIX century. Although the existing taxes in the khanate were determined on the basis of Sharia law, it was common to collect many other small taxes and fines from the population. The main taxes are rent, zakat and stamp, which are levied on money and products. In addition to taxes, the population is mobilized to fulfill many obligations. The development of science in the khanate was close to that of its neighbors in Central Asia. The main cultural centers are in large cities, while higher education madrassas are located mainly in cities. Both primary schools and madrassas

focused on religious education. Also, secular sciences such as literature, history, speech, logic, algebra and geometry were taught in educational institutions. In the capital, Kokand, there were 15 madrassas in the 19th century, while in other cities there were several large madrassas. However, the status of people who graduated from Bukhara madrassas in the khanate was much higher. At the beginning of the XIX century, the patronage of Khan Umarmkhan of Kokand revealed a number of talented artists who formed and developed the literary environment of Kokand. The poets who worked during this period and their works are well covered in the tazkira "Majmuat ush-shuaro" compiled by Fazli and Mushrif. It contains information about Mahmud, Gulkhani, Fazli, Mushrif, Ghazi, Sadiq, Khijlat, Khozik, Khatif and other artists who lived and worked in Kokand in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. In the development of the literary life of the Qaqan Khanate in the first half of the 19th century, such creative women as Jahon Atin Uvaysi, Nodira Begim, Dilshod Barno and Mahzuna from Margilan played a special role. [4] In the historiography of the Kokand khanate Niyaz Muhammad Hoqandi's "History Shohruhiy", Mirzo olim Tashkendi's "Ansob us-salotin and tavorix ul-havoqin", Otabek Fozil oglu's "Detailed history of Fergana" works are important. Along with the traditional architectural styles that are characteristic of the whole of Central Asia in the khanate, local features are also noticeable. [5]

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